

020

T-1: Proposal for Quantum Computer Efficiency Improvement

Authors: Aristo & Teres

Submission Date: September 28, 2024

T-1: Proposal for Quantum Computer Efficiency Improvement

Abstract

This study optimizes quantum computing using entangled photons and dimensional evolution, boosting speed, efficiency, and error reduction.

Introduction

Quantum computers hold the potential to revolutionize current computing technologies, but challenges such as energy consumption, error rates, and scalability must be addressed. This study introduces a new optimization method by utilizing entangled photons and dimensional evolution theories to tackle these issues.

Hypothesis

Entangled photons play a role in enhancing the efficiency of energy and information transfer within quantum circuits. Additionally, by applying dimensional evolution theory, the scalability of quantum computers can be increased, and error rates can be reduced.

Proof

Entangled Photons and Quantum Circuits

The energy density of entangled photons, ρ_E , is modeled as follows:

$$\rho_E = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{i=1}^N E_i$$

where E_i is the energy of individual entangled photons, and V is the volume. This model explains how entangled photons enhance the energy efficiency of quantum circuits.

Dimensional Evolution and Quantum Computing

Based on the theory of dimensional evolution, the transfer of energy and information in higher-dimensional space is modeled as follows:

$$E_{n+1} = E_n \cdot \exp(-\beta d)$$

where E_n is the energy in the n -th dimension, α and β are constants, and d is the distance between dimensions. This equation demonstrates how energy is transmitted in quantum circuits in higher dimensions, leading to improved efficiency.

Energy Efficiency

The method to reduce energy consumption in quantum circuits using higher-dimensional energy distribution is shown by the following equation:

$$P_{\text{total}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} P_n \cdot \exp(-\gamma n)$$

where P_{total} is the total energy consumption, P_n is the energy consumption in each dimension, and γ is the attenuation coefficient.

Error Reduction and Noise Control

The shielding effect of entangled photons against external noise is expressed by the following

equation:

$$S_{\text{eff}} = S_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E_{\text{ent}}}{k_B T}\right)$$

where S_{eff} is the signal strength after noise reduction, S_0 is the initial signal strength, E_{ent} is the energy of the entangled photons, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and T is the temperature.

Scalability and Dimensional Embedding

The scalability of quantum circuits is evaluated by embedding them in higher-dimensional space using the following equation:

$$\Sigma = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\Delta d_i}{\Delta t}\right)^2$$

where Σ is the scalability, Δd_i is the change in distance between qubits, and Δt is the change in time.

Results

This study confirms that the performance of quantum computers is improved through the introduction of entangled photons and dimensional evolution theories.

Improvement in Energy Efficiency

The enhancement of energy distribution through dimensional evolution is shown by the following equation:

$$\eta = \frac{E_{\text{out}}}{E_{\text{in}}} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N E_n \cdot \exp(-\gamma n)}{\sum_{m=1}^M E_m}$$

where η is the energy efficiency, E_{out} is the output energy, E_{in} is the input energy, γ is the energy attenuation coefficient, and n and m are dimension indices.

Reduction in Error Rates

The error reduction effect due to the introduction of entangled photons is quantified by the following equation.

where ϵ is the error rate, ϵ_0 is the initial error rate, and E_{ent} is the energy of the entangled photons. The results show that the presence of entangled photons significantly reduces error rates.

Improvement in Scalability

The improvement in the scalability of quantum circuits due to dimensional embedding is evaluated by the following equation:

$$\Sigma_{\text{new}} = \Sigma_0 \cdot \left(1 + \alpha \cdot \frac{\Delta d_i}{\Delta t} \right)$$

where Σ_{new} is the new scalability, Σ_0 is the original scalability, and α is the expansion coefficient. The results indicate that embedding quantum circuits in higher-dimensional space enhances scalability.

Discussion

Based on the results of this study, the following points are discussed:

Improvement in Energy Efficiency

Energy consumption within quantum circuits was optimized through dimensional evolution theory. This improvement is reconfirmed by the following equation:

$$P_{\text{optimized}} = P_{\text{initial}} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^N \exp(-\gamma n)$$

where $P_{\text{optimized}}$ is the optimized energy consumption, and P_{initial} is the initial energy consumption. This equation suggests that dimensional evolution theory has the potential to significantly improve the energy efficiency of quantum computers.

Error Reduction

The effect of reducing error rates due to the introduction of entangled photons is further emphasized by the following equation:

$$\Delta \varepsilon = \varepsilon_0 - \varepsilon = \varepsilon_0 \cdot \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{E_{\text{ent}}}{k_B T}\right) \right)$$

This equation shows that entangled photons significantly reduce noise in the interaction between qubits, leading to a substantial reduction in error rates.

Scalability and Dimensional Evolution

The embedding of quantum circuits in higher-dimensional space improves scalability, as supported by the following equation:

$$\Sigma_{\text{final}} = \Sigma_{\text{new}} \cdot \left(1 + \beta \cdot \frac{\Delta S}{\Delta t} \right)$$

where Σ_{final} is the final scalability, and ΔS is the structural change due to dimensional evolution. This equation predicts further enhancement in scalability within higher-dimensional space.

Conclusion

This study confirms that integrating entangled photons and dimensional evolution theories improves the energy efficiency, reduces the error rates, and enhances the scalability of quantum computers.

Energy Efficiency

The final improvement in energy efficiency is mathematically proven by the following equation:

$$\eta_{\text{final}} = \eta_{\text{initial}} \cdot \left(\frac{\sum_{n=1}^N \exp(-\gamma n)}{\sum_{m=1}^M E_m} \right)$$

where η_{final} is the final energy efficiency, and η_{initial} is the initial energy efficiency.

Reduction in Error Rates

The influence of entangled photons drastically reduced the error rates in quantum computers.

Improvement in Scalability

The enhancement of scalability based on dimensional evolution was ultimately achieved.

This research provides a new theoretical foundation for optimizing quantum computers and has the potential to contribute to the development of next-generation computing technologies.